

PHRASEAL VERB AS PART OF PHRASEOLOGICAL ENGLISH
LANGUAGE SYSTEMS

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Annotation. This article is dedicated to the analysis of English phrasal verbs and understanding their nature as part of the theory of English phraseology. It demonstrates that phrasal verbs play a dual role within English phraseology: they can be classified as idioms due to their imagery and conciseness in conveying information, and as phraseological units because of their grammatical structure. The study of phrasal verbs within the framework of English phraseology theory should develop within the science of linguoculturology, which is characterized by anthropocentric communicative aspects.

Key words: linguoculturology; phraseology; idioms; phraseological units; phrasal verbs; adverbial postposition.

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена анализу английских фразовых глаголов и пониманию их природы в рамках теории английской фразеологии. Показано, что фразовые глаголы играют в английской фразеологии двойную роль: их можно отнести к идиомам благодаря их образности и лаконичности передачи информации, и к фразеологическим единицам из-за их грамматического строя. Изучение фразовых глаголов в рамках теории английской фразеологии должно развиваться в рамках науки лингвокультурологии, для которой характерны антропоцентрические коммуникативные аспекты.

Ключевые слова: лингвокультурология; фразеология; идиомы; фразеологизмы; фразовые глаголы; деепричастный послелог.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ingliz frazeologiyasi nazariyasining bir qismi sifatida ingliz frazemalarini tahlil qilish va ularning mohiyatini tushunishga bag'ishlangan. Bu frazemalarning ingliz frazeologiyasi tarkibida ikki tomonlama rol o'ynashini ko'rsatadi: ularni tasviriyligi va axborotni etkazishdagi ixchamligi tufayli idiomalar, grammatik tuzilishiga ko'ra esa frazeologik birliklar sifatida tasniflash mumkin. Ingliz frazeologiyasi nazariyasi doirasida frazemalarni o'rganish antropotsentrik kommunikativ jihatlari bilan ajralib turadigan lingvokulturologiya fani doirasida rivojlanishi kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: lingvokulturologiya; frazeologiya; idiomalar; frazeologik birliklar; frazema fe'llar; ergash gap.

The development of an anthropocentric paradigm has shifted linguistic problems towards focusing on humans and their place in culture. Language shapes linguistic identity, which can be reconstructed in its main features based on linguistic means. Speech, as the external manifestation of language, is considered "among all aspects of cultural heritage the most fundamental" [8, p. 8], as it is a necessary prerequisite for the existence of culture. In every utterance, the speaker is presented as a personality with unique ethnic, national, cultural characteristics, worldviews, and axiological orientations. Thus, within this paradigm, language is understood primarily as a code, a fundamental manifestation of culture within various linguistic signs and symbols, alongside the visual manifestations of the collective's culture, and is considered a "culture-determined behavior system" [2, p. 43]. The constituent elements of the cultural linguistic code, linguistic signs of any complexity level, and particularly phraseological units, contain information necessary for understanding the behavior of cultural collective members.

Phraseological units reflect the history, lifestyle, and national mentality of a people, "its original means and unique, indigenous wealth" [6, p. 265]. As linguistic units containing high cultural-value and emotional content, phraseological units can be defined as a repository of the linguistic personality's cultural-value representations of the surrounding world. A distinctive feature of phraseological units is their stability and semantic integrity, making them reproduced as semantically indivisible speech units. From the perspective of enriching the language and updating its vocabulary, phraseological units serve as the basis for new formations, made possible "by reinterpreting the meanings of the words comprising the phraseological unit" [1, pp. 8-21]. The study of English phraseological combinations, whose meanings cannot be explained from grammatical and logical points of view, falls under the science of phraseology.

Phraseology is a branch of linguistics that examines functionally and semantically indivisible combinations in terms of their origin, structure, semantics, style, and pragmatics of use. English phraseology represents a coherent system within the more complex system of the national language, as part of its various levels. It includes various groups of phraseological units, categorized by their characteristic linguistic (unambiguous and polysemous, homonymous, synonymous, antonymous) and stylistic (stylistically marked and

neutral) features [10, p. 99], but significantly differing in stylistic coloration and stylistic affiliation.

One group of English phraseological units is phrasal verbs, complex lexical units consisting of a meaningful verb and a postposition expressed by a preposition (e.g., put up – raise, build, erect [4], get out – leave, escape, manage, look after – take care of, oversee) or adverb (e.g., step aside – step aside, be away – succeed, have a big chance of success, ponder). Phrasal verb combinations arise in great numbers and "completely transform the English language" [1, p. 32]. Therefore, in learning this language by representatives of other linguistic cultures, mastering phrasal verbs is essential for ensuring speech dynamism. Phrasal verbs significantly contribute to communication success due to their emotional expressiveness and expanded semantic capabilities, along with their conciseness.

When discussing phrasal verbs as part of the English phraseological system, it is essential to consider the nature and scope of the concept of phrasal verbs, namely, to which type of phrases phrasal verbs should be attributed.

The idiomatic nature of an expression is "defined as the inability to derive the overall meaning of a fixed word combination from the sum of the meanings of its lexical components <...>; as the global nature of the nomination, which makes an idiomatic word combination similar to a single word, and as literal untranslatability into other languages" [4, p. 11]. For instance, the verbs "to act" – "to act, clown around, cause a scene" [3, p. 8], and "to grow" – "to grow" form idiomatic phrasal verbs such as "act up" – "to malfunction (of a mechanism)" [7, p. 173], and "grow on" – "to become liked, loved", whose meanings differ from those of the base verbs. However, it is not feasible to consider phrasal verbs as pure idioms.

Some phrasal verbs possess certain features of phraseological unity, including complete lexical indivisibility. Substituting the postposition in such a phrasal verb, or replacing the base verb with a synonym, either destroys the imagery of the phrasal verb or alters its expressive meaning.

According to "The Oxford Thesaurus: An A-Z Dictionary of Synonyms" edited by L. Urdang [7, p. 1891], the verb "to take" has 40 synonym rows containing 151 synonyms. Replacing the base verb in the phrasal verb "to take away" – "to remove, take away, carry away, lead away, make worse, spoil" [3, p. 793] with any of the 12 synonymous verbs forms phrasal verbs with meanings different from the original: "to bear away" – "to win, emerge victorious" [4], "to get away" – "to get out of a difficult situation, escape unscathed, take a leave", "to

catch away" – "obsolete. to drag away, carry away", "to clear away" – "to clear away" [Ibid], "to draw away" – "to move away, depart (from a station), set sail (from a dock)", "to drink away" – "to drink away", "to eat away" – "to consume", "to lead away" – "to captivate, lead away", "to move away" – "to change one's viewpoint", "to steal away" – "to slip away unnoticed", "to think away" – "to dismiss from one's mind", and "to win away" – "to take away, snatch, seize". Additionally, the verb "to take," according to the "Oxford Phrasal Verb Dictionary," forms phrasal verbs with various meanings with 27 collocates (postpositions). This variability of meanings clearly demonstrates the impossibility of substituting either the base or the adverbial part of the phrasal verb. However, in some cases, such substitutions create favorable conditions for individual stylistic updates in speech, widely used in cinematography for creating wordplay. Consider the following example:

- Hello, where have you been [4, 3.40]?
- Oh, that was important business. But I'll be around right from now.
- Hello, where have you been?
- Oh, I had to leave for important business. But I'll be back soon

(literally – I'll be around you).

Thus, according to the "Oxford Phrasal Verb Dictionary," the phrasal verb "be around" does not exist as an independent unit; however, there is a reference to the phrasal verb "to be over" [3, p. 12] – "to come, visit (someone's home)" [4], as a synonymous phraseological combination. Replacing the preposition "over" with the adverbial postposition "round" – "around" [3, p. 678] adds an extra-linguistic meaning "to be constantly around someone" to the statement, inherent to this adverb.

The meaning of some phrasal verbs, like phraseological combinations, can be derived from the meanings of their lexical components. For example, the phrasal verb "dawn away" – "to fade away, to die out (about a conversation)" [7, p. 190] is formed from the combination of the verb "to dawn" – "to dawn" [3, p. 192] and the adverb "away" – "away (denoting a distance from the place of action)" [Ibid, p. 45], or the phrasal verb "lean back" – "to lean back" [7, p. 212] is formed from the combination of the verb "to lean" – "to lean, to incline" [3, p. 448] and the adverb "away" – "away (denoting a distance from the place of action)" [Ibid, p. 45].

Similarly, to collocations, one part of a phrasal verb may be replaceable. Since the main meaning is contained in the verb, and the direction of the action is in the adverbial postposition, it is often the verb part of the phrase that gets

replaced. For instance, "to write something down," according to the "Russian-English Dictionary" edited by A. I. Smirnitsky, can be translated into English with phrasal verbs like "to take down, put down, jot down, and write down" [5, p. 239]. However, in some cases, various postpositions can be added to the same base verb while maintaining the original meaning. Thus, the variants of the phrasal verb "to pass away" – "to pass out" and "to pass over" preserve the denotative meaning "to die, to pass away" [3, p. 568].

Phrasal verbs, as fixed speech units with a constant composition, are often used in sentences with specific instructions, admonitions, or wishes, due to their high emotional content.

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